

QUICK PHOTO GUIDE TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN *ISOXYA* SPECIES

Compiled by Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (Dippenaaransie@gmail.com)

For more information and credits for photographs used see:

DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A. S., HADDAD, C. R., FOORD, S. H., LOTZ, L. N. & WEBB, P. (2022). *The Araneidae of South Africa*. Version 2: part 2 (E-Ne). South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide, Irene, 64 pp. <https://doi:10.5281/zenodo.6619195>

1. *Isoxya cicatricosa* (C. L. Koch, 1844)

2. *Isoxya mossamedensis* Benoit, 1962

Sisyphus Table Mountain Female and male

3. *Isoxya mucronata* Walckenaer, 1841

Habitus after Emerit (1982)

- The cephalothorax lacks a longitudinal groove. The anterior edge of the body is slightly undulated; lateral edges are mildly curved. The median area of the abdomen is progressively elevated and humped.
- Spines 1 and 2 are very short and stand vertically. Spines B are short and spaced apart, located between sigilla 7 and 8.
- The abdomen is broader than it is long, bordered by 19 sigilla. The odd sigillum (the 10th counted from right to left) is positioned in the middle of the posterior edge.
- Sigilla 1 to 6 are elongated; sigilla 2 to 10 are rounded. Sigilla 1 to 4 are along the anterior edge of the carapace, between the mid
- The cephalothorax is reddish-brown. The abdomen is mostly yellow. The legs are light brown except for the tips of the femur, patella, tibia, and the end of tarsus I, which are darkened. The sternum is yellowish. The specimen from Katanga has uniformly dark legs.

FROM INATURALIST ?

4. *Isoxya semiflava* Simon, 1887

Simon, 1887

Simon 1895: 873

Benoit, 1962: 22

SANSA no records

FROM INATURALIST ?

Do this one fit in?

5. *Isoxya stuhlmanni* Bosenberg & Lenz, 1895

FROM INATURALIST

6. *Isoxya tabulata* (Thorell, 1859)

FROM INATURALIST

7. *Isoxya yatesi* Emerit, 1973

- Decorations: prosoma, chelicerae, sigillae, epigyne, and spinneret ring black.
- Scutum orange-red (appears bright yellow in life) with black granulation.
- Legs brown, with the distal parts of the long segments black, displaying metallic violet reflections; sternum pale yellow.
- Opisthosoma globular in lateral view;
- spines small, conical, acute, and nearly equal in size
- The first two pairs are erect vertically, while the last pair is horizontal, positioned atop strong granular protuberances that protrude significantly relative

FROM INATURALIST ??